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v2.0	01/09/2025	KVC, CETEC	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, resubmitted to EC, including the explanation for why ViSS solution performed significantly worse than the benchmark, along with proposed mitigation measures (page 20). Additionally, a new mention has been added to subsection 4.1.2 indicating that future LCA iterations will include energy consumption (page 15), and the beginning of Section 6 has been modified to improve the clarity of the LCC (page 36).

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Executive summary

Based on ViSS D6.3 SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework, the present report presents the first iteration of sustainable by design assessment. It covers environmental, social, and economic dimensions while security dimension is assessed in D6.6 (also presented in M18 of ViSS project). The present assessment has been the opportunity to implement for the first time ViSS scoring system which consists in comparing how ViSS value chain performs in comparison to the market benchmark for the environmental dimension and a reference for the social dimension.

The environmental sustainability in the SSbD framework is based on the life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology which is commonly used and standardized with ISO standards. LCA comprises of four stages: goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory, life cycle impact assessment and interpretation of the results. The first LCA iteration of the ViSS PHBV production chain shows that its environmental impacts are significantly higher than the fossil benchmark, primarily due to limited process data. The redesign of the ViSS process is necessary, focusing on improving fermentation yields, chemical regeneration, and energy efficiency. Future iterations will consider additional benchmarks, including polymer quality and technical properties and will include energy consumption as a factor. The functional unit might need adjustment for specific applications. Additionally, including the use and end-of-life stages in future LCA iterations will be essential to assess the biodegradation impact of ViSS PHBV. The first social sustainability assessment of ViSS is preliminary. However, it shows promising results. Key areas for improvement include migrant workforce integration, supplier audits, Corporate Social Responsibility policies, and governance. The social dimension evaluation faces challenges like a narrow organizational focus, limited representativeness, and difficulties using proxy data for the comparison. Data scarcity hinders progress assessment, and the organizational-level focus restricts the scope of indicators. To improve, additional use cases from literature and EU/national projects are needed for clearer conclusions. The economic sustainability assessment is still in its early stages and more detailed economic assessment of the ViSS solution will be possible later in a higher TRL and more information becomes available. Currently, only a few of the total costs have been reported, as cost data is limited at this stage of development. The economic assessment will be closely linked to the environmental sustainability assessment and ViSS scoring system will be applied to economic indicators.

Overall, although at an early stage, ViSS solution has potential to be a sustainable alternative to conventional market products. As well, ViSS SSbD framework has proven to be adapted to undertake the assessment of ViSS solution.

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1. List of abbreviations

A2C	Agro2Circular
BREF	Best Available Techniques Reference
CED	Cumulative energy demand
cSbD	Sustainability costing by design
eLCA	Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
eLCC	Environmental Life Cycle Costing
eSbD	Environmental sustainability by design
GHS	Globally Harmonized System
GWP	Global warming potential
ILO	International Labour Organization
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
NGIB	Next-Generation Industrial Biotechnology
OEF	Organisation Environmental Footprint
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
S-SbD	Social sustainability by design
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SO-LCA	Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment
SSbD	Safe and sustainable by design
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VFA	Volatile Fatty Acid

2. Introduction

Environmental challenges (e.g. climate change, ecosystem degradation and air and water pollution) related to human activity have arisen, but these challenges must be addressed by society at different levels, from individuals to policy makers and the industry, through the integration of different considerations in decision-making [1] [2]. In this context, *“the importance of adopting a life cycle approach and the development and implementation of policies for resource efficiency, environmentally sound waste management”* was recognized by the United Nations in 2012 [3]. A variety of tools, methodologies and indicators have been developed with the objective of assessing the impacts generated by human related activities [4] [5]. Moreover, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is also an opportunity to undertake the transition towards circular economy [6]. However, LCA is insufficient to tackle the full spectrum of sustainability challenges. The need for a perspective wider than the environmental LCA [7] was formalized into Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) framework as the combination of the three life cycle approaches: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) in a common framework to analyse the complete sustainability performance of the product or process system [8].

ViSS SSbD was presented in the Deliverable D6.3 (SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework (SRL)). The preliminary Safety assessment is presented in D6.6 whereas the preliminary environmental, social and economic assessments are presented in the present document. In the figure below, adapted from ViSS D6.3, the methodological steps followed by ViSS SSbD are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 ViSS SSbD framework construction (source: adapted from A2C D6.3)

The present deliverable proposes also a first attempt for the scoring system of ViSS SSbD approach. This scoring system is based on the latest JRC recommendations [9] that we apply as follows (from worst to best performance): 0: red colour; 1: orange; 2: yellow; 3: green; and 4: blue (see Figure 2). According to the mentioned recommendations, we consider that indicators that score 0 or 1 fail to improve the market reference, while indicators that score 2, 3 or 4 perform better than the market reference and pass. In the present deliverable we have only used this scoring system to S-LCA and LCA. Because there is not an established systematic way to score the S-LCA we are proposing an attempting score following the identified gap with the reference for each individual indicator. In future iterations of the

Figure 2 ViSS SSbD framework construction and assessment: methodology (source: adapted from A2C D6.3)

sustainability assessment the LCC will be included as well as the Safety dimension. The results of the assessment will be included and disclosed in the ICT Tool.

ViSS technological developments are still under research and not mature enough as the project is currently at the first stage of implementation (M18). However, for exploratory and screening purposes, a ViSS value chain (Section 2) has been subjected to the sustainability assessment, namely LCA (Section 3), S-LCA (Section 4) and LCC (Section 4). Although initial, this screening is the opportunity to pilot in a realistic environment the indicators and measurements selected in the evaluation framework and the data gathering procedures. Thus, the results presented in this deliverable are considered as a first step, and only when the development of the ViSS solution will reach a more mature stage, a complete evaluation will be possible and will be delivered in M47.

3. ViSS value chain

Due to the processes involved in ViSS project a value chain has been identified for the screening stage of the LCSA attending to the following criteria:

1. TRL Level: The processes in the value chains selected have reached the industrial or sub-industrial scale and ViSS solutions have currently a TRL5-6. Considering this and the EC indications

[9] (Figure 3) the present assessment relates to an Intermediate SSbD assessment where not all the characteristics of the product will be assessed.

Figure 3 TRL and SSbD assessment levels [9]

2. **Availability of data:** This criterion is closely related with the previous one, since at early TRLs there is a low availability of data at implementation stage (beyond design/laboratory), as well as a limited number of identified benchmarks with which the developed process can be compared.

3. **Circularity of processes:** the value chain presents a higher degree of circularity, since they start and end (with upcycled raw material) in the agrifood industry in Spain. This also responds to the ViSS objective of enabling the territorial deployment of the multidimensional solution integrating the scaled-up technologies, to be later validated and replicated in other territorial contexts.

The partners that are involved in this value chain (Figure 4) and have provided data for the LCSA are CETEC, CETBIO and IRIS:

- **IRIS** is an advanced engineering company (SME) specialized in the manufacture and integration of Process Analytical Technology (PAT)-based real-time quality monitoring solutions for the process industries. IRIS will lead the production of volatile fatty acids (VFAs) (as feedstocks for the PHBV range production) from sugar residues by an innovative technology, including the process optimisation and scale up to the PHBV demo plant. Moreover, IRIS has a vast experience in the development of photonic solutions for plastics sorting. In ViSS IRIS develops a protocol sorting to allow the identification and sorting of the new PHBV packaging in the future recycling facilities.
- **CETBIO** is a SME focused on the production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) biopolymers, PHBV, by using next-generation industrial biotechnology (NGIB) strategies. They are involved in the bioplastic PHBV production from residues, including the processes (fermentation, downstream) optimisation and support in the start-up & operation of the PHBV production demo plant. Moreover, they will oversee the PHBV formulation scale up to achieve a stable PHBV range.
- **CETEC** (Project Coordinator) is a Technological Centre specialized in plastics and bioplastics with a broad experience in project management (6 H2020 projects coordinated). CETEC leads the technical activities linked to PHBV bioplastic behaviour for flexible packaging developed by extrusion and thermoforming, leading the eco-design approach. Moreover,

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CETEC develops the ICT platform and leads the engineering and construction of the PHBV production plant (Demo1). It also assists other partners as Project Coordinator.

Figure 4 ViSS value chain

4. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

4.1 LCA methodology and eSbD framework

4.1.1 LCA

The environmental sustainability in the SSbD framework is based on the life cycle assessment (LCA) methodology which is commonly used and standardized with ISO 14040-44 standards (ISO 14040 [10], ISO 14044 [11]). LCA comprises of four stages, namely goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory, life cycle impact assessment and interpretation of the results, which are interlinked and iterative (see Figure 5).

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Figure 5 Methodological overview¹ [12]

LCA considers the environmental impacts created over the whole life cycle of a product, i.e. from cradle to grave while covering the raw material production, transportation, production, distribution, usage and end-of-life handling. In addition to the ISO-standards, the European Commission [13] has provided more detailed guidance for LCA used for Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) calculations. The main principles of the LCA standards and PEF guidance are also used in the SSbD framework and the ViSS project.

4.1.2 Environmental Sustainability by Design (eSbD)

Environmental Sustainability by Design (eSbD) considers the 16 different environmental impacts suggested in the European commission’s Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) guideline (European Commission, 2021). They are grouped into toxicity, climate change, pollution, and resource use in the eSbD framework [14]. In addition, Cumulative energy demand (CED) is considered in the resources category in the ViSS eSbD shown in Table 1. The eSbD used in ViSS is described in more detail in A2C D6.3 *SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework.v1.0* [15].

Table 1 The categories in eSbD design and the corresponding aspects with units assessed in eSbD

eSbD category	Aspects (Impact category)	Unit
Toxicity	Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh
	Human toxicity, non cancer	CTUh
	Ecotoxicity	CTUe
Climate change	Climate change	kg CO ₂ -eq
Pollution	Ozone depletion	kg CFC ⁻¹¹ -eq
	Particulate matter	disease incidence
	Ionizing radiation	kBq U ₂₃₅ -eq
	Photochemical ozone formation	kg NM _{VOC} -eq
	Acidification	mol H ⁺ -eq
	Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N-eq
	Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P-eq
	Eutrophication, marine	kg N-eq

¹ To report the LCA in line with ISO 14040/44 increases reliability and allows verification of the study’s assumptions, as well as compliance.

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Resources		
	Water use	m ³ world eq deprived
	Land use	
	Resource use, fossil	MJ, net calorific value
	Resource use, minerals, and metals	kg Sb-eq
	Cumulative energy demand (CED) ²	MJ oil-eq./m ² a

According to the *Safe and Sustainable by Design chemicals and materials framework* [16], the performance of the assessed product is evaluated against a reference i.e. benchmark product as the reduction of the impacts. There are several possibilities for the reference product depending on the intended application of the product.

As the SSbD evaluation in ViSS project is done in three phases and since the production processes are being developed with limited data availability, this first phase of evaluation focuses on the laboratory scale material streams only and the energy consumption is excluded. The next phases are expected to include also the energy flows and a wider system boundary. In addition, multiple reference products may be used in the next phases of eSbD of ViSS once the product application becomes clearer.

4.2 Case description

LCA is carried out to evaluate the value chain of ViSS PHBV bioplastic. Currently, ViSS production is developed in laboratory scale. The process chart of current production is shown in Figure 6. The ViSS value chain uses sugar rich liquor waste and poultry bones and feathers as feedstocks for PHBV production. The sugar rich liquor waste is first conditioned and then added to fermenter together with other nutrients to produce volatile fatty acids (VFAs). VFAs, hydrolyzed bones and feathers and sugar rich liquor waste are then added to the fermentative processes to grow the biomass to obtain the target PHBV range by *Haloferax Mediterranei* (*Hfx. Mediterranei*). The biomass is separated from the excess liquid phase and dried. After separation, PHBV is extracted from the biomass via solid-liquid extraction, and it is dried to form raw PHBV granulates.

In this first iteration of LCA, only mass balances are included in the assessment. The system boundary is set from cradle to gate of the production of 1kg raw PHBV, which was also set as functional unit of this calculation. Due to limited data availability and the process development, certain unit processes part of the VFA process and water and chemical recycling were excluded from the assessment. Moreover, the purification process step was excluded from the assessment for the same reason (indicated by grey box in Figure 6). The transportation of materials used in production are included in the ecoinvent version 3.10 (2023)³ market for -datasets utilized in the assessment. The emission factor data was taken from ecoinvent 3.10 database and Sulca 5.3⁴ was used for modelling with EF3.1 LCA methodology.

² Proposed in ViSS SSbD workshop (March 2024).

³ ecoinvent database version 3.10. (2023). Requires a license. Available at: www.ecoinvent.org

⁴ <https://www.semantum.fi/products/SULCA/>

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Due to the developing nature of the ViSS process, there are some limitations and uncertainties regarding the assessment. Energy balance was not accounted for in the assessment due to laboratory scale equipment and non-optimized energy consumption, therefore the CED indicator could not be considered at this point. Sugar rich liquor waste and bones and feathers were treated as a waste so they did not have an innate emission burden. In addition, cell debris waste from solid-liquid extraction were cut-off (indicated by light grey box in Figure 6). Most of the chemicals used in the VISS process are from ecoinvent 3.10 as shown in Annex 1. IRIS solvent 1 modeled as fatty acid produced from soybean oil, palm oil and palm kernel oil in ecoinvent. IRIS solvent 2 was modelled as chemical, organic.

A fossil-based alternative was chosen as a reference product for comparison of the impact assessment results to assess the environmental sustainability. Polypropylene (PP) has characteristics and applications similar to those of PHBV. Benchmark LCIA values were obtained from “market for polypropylene, granulate, GLO” dataset from ecoinvent 3.10 database. The benchmark product consists fully of virgin material of fossil origin.

In the benchmark LCA dataset for PP, system boundaries cover cradle-to-gate activities and transportation activities, including supply to consumers. The dataset has been constructed using a mix of PP production technologies commercially available: slurry suspension polymerisation, bulk suspension polymerisation of liquid monomers, and gas phase polymerisation using Ziegler-Natta and Metallocene catalysts. Differing from the PHBV screening LCA described in this deliverable, energy and water balance had been included in the PP life cycle inventory in addition to mass balance. The functional unit of the PP dataset is 1kg of PP. The impact assessment method EF3.1 was applied in the benchmark assessment.

The process and system boundaries of the assessed PHBV system compared to the benchmark PP system are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Process chart of ViSS PHBV system and benchmark fossil polypropylene system. Grey boxes are excluded due to lack of data at this point of the project.

4.3 Results

The contribution analysis for the ViSS PHBV enriched biomass for all studied impact categories is shown in Figure 7. In all impact categories, the most important life cycle stage is VFA separation. It causes 78-97% of the impacts in all impact categories. The impacts in that life cycle stage are caused by IRIS solvent 1 modelled as fatty acids and IRIS solvent 2 production modelled as organic chemical. The major cause behind the impacts of those two substances is the usage amount: approximately 360-420 kg of each substance are used in production of 1 kg of raw PHBV. When studying especially the impact category of global warming potential, IRIS solvent 1 modeled as fatty acid causes enormous impact since produced from soybean oil, palm oil and palm kernel oil in ecoinvent causing major land use change -related GWP impacts.

Figure 7 Contribution analysis by life cycle stages of ViSS PHBV enriched biomass.

When the absolute impacts are normalized and weighted with EF3.1 factors, the greatest contributors are climate change, energy resources, freshwater ecotoxicity, and ionization radiation as shown in Figure 8.

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Figure 8 Normalised and weighted results of VISS PHBV.

The goal of SSbD is to enable producing safe and sustainable chemicals and materials by comparing the product under development to benchmark products. For this deliverable, impact reduction criteria have not yet been established, as laboratory-scale production is anticipated to exhibit greater environmental impacts compared to the full-scale benchmark production of fossil polymers. However, ‘no improvement’ is commonly viewed as failing the criteria and therefore as score 0, which is indicated with the colour red in the comparison shown in table 2. This first iteration of LCA is used to start data gathering from production partners and to get the first insights into the emission hotspots of planned production. In Table 2, the impacts of 1 kg VISS raw PHBV are compared to benchmark product of 1 kg fossil-based polypropylene (PP). Due to confidentiality restrictions on benchmark impacts, instead of using absolute values, we used scalar values to simplify comparisons. We set a benchmark impacts value to 1, and then scaled the ViSS results relative to this benchmark.

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Table 2 Comparison of scaled impacts of ViSS product to benchmark polypropylene product (ecoinvent 3.10). The cells are highlighted with red if the impact of ViSS product is greater than the benchmark value and thus is score 0.

eSbD category	Aspect (Impact category)	Benchmark PP scaled impact	ViSS raw PHBV scaled impact
Toxicity	ecotoxicity: freshwater	1	2926
	ecotoxicity: freshwater, inorganics	1	448
	ecotoxicity: freshwater, organics	1	29080
	human toxicity: carcinogenic	1	1788
	human toxicity: carcinogenic, inorganics	1	549
	human toxicity: carcinogenic, organics	1	1828
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic	1	1021
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, inorganics	1	656
	human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, organics	1	4840
Climate change	climate change	1	783
	climate change: biogenic	1	4875
	climate change: fossil	1	485
	climate change: land use and land use change	1	597708
Pollution	acidification	1	825
	eutrophication: freshwater	1	630
	eutrophication: marine	1	3104
	eutrophication: terrestrial	1	1096
	ionising radiation: human health	1	485
	ozone depletion	1	599
	particulate matter formation	1	929
	photochemical oxidant formation: human health	1	577
Resource use	energy resources: non-renewable	1	384
	land use	1	7027
	material resources: metals/minerals	1	716
	water use	1	1828

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When compared to benchmark, VISS PHBV performs drastically worse across all impact categories. As shown by contribution analysis in Figure 7, most of the impacts come from separation of VFAs due to such low chemical usage efficiency. However, also the other chemical usage is to be lowered if reductions compared to benchmark are to be achieved.

Together with each technical partner, redesign needs were discussed and potential solutions were identified. The solvent recycling cycles in separation of VFAs will be increased up to 4. In addition, the ratio between solvent and fermented liquid will be lowered to 1:1, implying a significant decrease in the amount of solvents used. If those measures are still not sufficient, a solvent-free recovery will be tested as well. In PHBV fermentation, tests will be done to improve the PHBV yield, thus lowering the amount of inputs needed. In addition, the glucose will be replaced with sufficient quantity of sugar rich liquor waste.

In addition to re-design solutions and expanded system boundary, the second LCA iteration will aim to improve the quality and accuracy of secondary data used in the assessment. More accurate secondary data e.g. on solvents 1 and 2 may reduce their impacts on the results. Before conducting the second SSbD assessment, the VISS PHBV production is planned to start a demo-scale production, thus enabling economics-of-scale in input usage as well.

5 Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)

As it has been previously presented, VISS LCA is in line with the ISO 14040/44 [12]: the alignment with international standards is critical if it is required for informing under a Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) approach. In the context of EU-27, LCA is also refined by Product Environmental Footprint (PEF)⁵ as well as the Organisation Environmental Footprint (OEF)⁶. Thus, whilst LCA focuses on environmental metrics, the analysis is also extended to social and economic metrics (S-LCA and LCC, respectively).

Following the definition provided by UNEP Handbook[17], S-LCA is “*a methodology to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle*”, delivering systematic data that can be operationalised through quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods. The concept arose in the 2000s[18], based on the attempt to build a comprehensive approach to product chains aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This insight is deeply connected to the three pillars of sustainability, in which S-LCA is supposed to deploy the interplay between industrial processes and social impacts, where the latter are mainly understood as the impacts on human capital, human well-being, cultural heritage and social behaviour[19].

S-LCA has raised the interest of decision makers from several areas, such as investment, business management, industrial management, consumers, NGOs and public policies[20]. For policymakers, SLCA could help to design policy measures (i.e. taxes) seeking to internalise externalities generated

⁵ https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/environmental-footprint-methods/pef-method_en

⁶ https://green-business.ec.europa.eu/environmental-footprint-methods/life-cycle-assessment-ef-methods_en

by a type or category of product. For businesses (manufacturers or service providers), S-LCA may serve to gather information for the design and implementation of strategies and actions related to the commitment of their Corporate Social Responsibility strategies; but also, to identify possible risks, such as adverse behavioural responses which could potentially undermine a business model. S-LCA is also important for citizens to take individual consumption decisions based on reliable information on how the products or services comply with desirable social norms (i.e. fair trade); in the case of NGOs, they may as verifiers, undertaking actions to ensure that these products have been generated, traded and processed in a way that lessens the negative impacts on sustainable development and boosts the positive ones [19].

Nevertheless, while the performance of an environmental LCA and economic LCC have been set out in detail by ISO standards [11] [21], there are no comparable standards or internationally recognized code of practice for S-LCA. Compared to environmental and economic aspects, social aspects present special challenges because they can be highly diverse and are weighed very differently according to the interest groups and/or countries and regions involved [22] [23]. In addition, the evaluation of social aspects is subjected to a greater variability over time compared to environmental assessment [18] [20] [22].

According to the proposal provided by the UNEP [24] and aligned with the LCA modelling schemes, the main points of the ViSS approach towards S-LCA are based on both the Methodological Sheets [25] and [26]. The methodology, framework and indicators were further detailed in D6.3 (Evaluation Framework), and the results will be explained together with the Life Cycle Costing (LCC) in this deliverable and future iterations.

S-LCA evaluates how each lifecycle affects stakeholders (i.e., workers, local communities, consumers, and society, as well as value chain actors), addressing issues concerning fairness, labor conditions, health and safety, or socioeconomic benefits and harms.

5.1 S-LCA in ViSS: general aim

S-LCA can be understood as a social assessment methodology aimed to evaluate the social aspects of production and their potential positive and negative impacts through their lifecycle [27]. The S-LCA can be implemented at product level or at organization level.

It is important to highlight that, while LCA is a well-established methodology, regulated by the ISO 14040 series of standards, and used in a wide variety of applications, S-LCA is still in a methodological consolidation phase [28] with only recent advances [29].

For this study, the social evaluation will be focused on the organization, following the approach so-called **Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA)** [26][27]. Recent literature provides several contributions and case studies to this methodology, but the main conclusion is the difficulty in identifying social indicators at the product level as social impacts usually occur at the organizational level. Therefore, the selected unit of analysis has been THE ORGANISATION. SO-LCA measures social indicators at the organizational level in order to assess the organization's social performance, hence it goes beyond the product perspective but considers the organization as a whole [24]. Thus, the overall goal of SO-LCA in ViSS is to analyse the performance of the

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organizations of the identified value chain in order to promote the improvement of social conditions and/or their contribution to the social development of each organisation’s stakeholders. Insights from the SO-LCA & the other social measurements will also contribute to define the ViSS ICT Tool.

ViSS SO-LCA analysis focuses on the principles, indicators and data already discussed and presented in ViSS D6.3 (Figure 9). In Figure 9, coloured boxes (orange and green) correspond to principles covered by specific social sustainability aspects.

SOCIAL STAKEHOLDER CATEGORIES		WORKERS	VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	SOCIETY	LOCAL COMMUNITY	CONSUMERS	
Social sustainability aspects		Forced labour Fair salary Working hours Equal opportunities/ Discrimination Health and Safety Social benefits, legal issues, social security Workers' rights... Sexual harassment Fair competition Promoting social responsibility Supplier relationships Respect intellectual property rights Wealth distribution Public commitment to sustainability issues Contributions to economic development Technology development Corruption Poverty alleviation Access to material resources Access to immaterial resources Delocalization and migration Cultural heritage Safe and healthy living conditions Community engagement Local employment Secure living conditions Health and Safety Feedback mechanism Transparency End-of-life responsibility Affordability					
Social sustainability principles	Health						
	Influence						
	Competence						
	Impartiality						
	Meaning-making						

Figure 9 Social sustainability principles and aspects (source: adapted from A2C D6.3)

For the sake of the exploratory and screening assessment expected in this deliverable, we simplified the indicators and data to collect for an early, low TRL, stage of the project. Table 3 below includes a summary of the SO-LCA indicators collected. The tools and methodology applied (questionnaires, data sheets) were adapted from a previous SO-LCA assessment implemented (A2C D7.8 [31]) by the partners in charge (see Annex 2).

Aspects covered by ViSS SO-LCA screening analysis from the complete SO-LCA are shown in Table 3 (see Annex 3 and Annex 4 for additional information on the selection process and the used indicators):

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Table 3 ViSS List of stakeholder categories, impact subcategories and indicators

DIMENSION	CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR
SOCIAL	Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month
		Working hours	Full-time staff
		Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality
		Health and safety	Occupational safety measures
			Lost time injury frequency rate
		Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations
		Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Collective Bargaining Agreement
	Value chain actors	Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported
		Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour
		Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility
			Suppliers audit
	Society	Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship
		Wealth distribution	Fair price definition
		Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues
	Local community	Contributions to economic development	Total taxation per capita
		Technology development	Technology transfer
			Investments in technology development/ transfer
	Consumers	Access to material resources	Environmental management system
		Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate
			Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community
		Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health
		Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation
			Number of meetings with community stakeholders
Local employment		Workforce hired locally	
Consumers	Secure living conditions	Spending on locally based suppliers	
	Health and safety	Security complaints by the community	
		Labelling	
	Consumer complaints	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	
Transparency	Organisation communication transparency		
	End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems	

5.2 SO-LCA implementation (preliminary)

5.2.1 Value chain screening analysis by category

ViSS preliminary SO-LCA includes the assessment of the three organizations involved in ViSS value chain. These organizations are anonymized and referred to as Organization 1, 2 and 3. The five social categories are covered: Workers, Value chain actors, Society, Local community, and Consumers. In

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Tables 4 to 13, the colours given to each indicator for each organization correspond to the scoring from lower to higher (as mentioned in Figure 2): 0: red; 1: orange; 2: yellow; 3: green; and 4: blue. Considering the lack of consensus based, systematized procedures and/or market benchmarks in the social dimensions for the assignment of the mentioned scoring (from 0 to 4), the team has implemented a qualitative assessment based on the search of comparative context data for different aspects. This qualitative assessment analyses the performance of ViSS value chain in social indicators and establishes the level of improvement or worsening conditions compared with relevant reference data. Therefore, those that score 0 or 1 fail to improve against the reference data, while indicators that score 2, 3 or 4 perform better than the reference data at different levels. Specific indications are given to each individual indicator.

5.2.1.1 Stakeholder category: WORKERS

In this category, occupational health and safety, fair wages, and general working conditions were collected, assessed and compared to the reference data (see Table 4 for screening phase results and Table 5 for the synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator).

Table 4 Workers category: aspects, indicators, results, and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Fair salary	POSITIVE	Organisation average wage, per month	5,068.0 €	3,878.8 €	4,320.0 €	The average wage in Spain		INE data, national scope, on the average wage (full costs model) in Spain
						2,050 € [32]	2024 3Q	
Working hours	POSITIVE	Full-time staff	94.7%	100%	85.3%	Full-time staff in Spain		Calculated as the ratio of full-time permanent staff against the total company workforce.
						88% [33]	2024 3Q	
Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	POSITIVE	Gender equality	47.4%	66.7%	28%	Women's employment rate in Spain		Calculated as the percentage of women (total national workforce)
						45.3% [34]	2024 3Q	
Health and Safety	POSITIVE	Occupational safety measures	1	1	1	No comparable data found		Occupational safety measures are mandatory in Spain for companies/institutions of this size.
	NEGATIVE	Lost time injury	0	0	0	Incidence rate in Spain, in Industry sector		INSST report on the injuries that occurred during work hours

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		frequency rate				4,473 ⁷	Oct 2024	
	POSITIVE	Presence of sufficient safety measures	1	1	1	National regulation: BOE-A-1995-24292 and RD39/19978		Safety measures are mandatory in Spain for companies/institutions of this size.
Social benefits, legal issues, social security	NEGATIVE	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	0	0	0	Social security infringement proceedings in Spain: labour relations		These data correspond to the reported infringement proceedings
						16.696 [35]	2022	
Workers' rights	POSITIVE	Collective Bargaining Agreement	1	1	0	Total number of CBA in Spain, in Manufacture Industry sector		In 2022 there were in Spain 191,501 companies in the industry sector ⁹ , therefore only 0.67% of them have a CBA.
						1092 ¹⁰ 1292	2023 2022	
Sexual harassment	NEGATIVE	Sexual harassment incidents reported	0	0	0	Actions against sexual harassment in Spain		Infractions reported during work hours and/or in the workplace
						810 [36]	2022	

The analysis reveals a generally higher social performance across the three organizations compared to the reference data, specifically in compensations, employment stability and safety, whilst gender equality showed a varied performance across the cases.

For instance, the **average monthly wages** across cases (€5,068, €3,878.83, and €4,320) significantly exceed the ES average (€2,128.37, 2022) as well as the full-time employment rates (94.70%, 100%, and 85.30%; ES: 56.06%, 2023).

The fair salary¹¹ was evaluated for the three partners involved in the ViSS value chain their monthly organization average wage and we compared it to the Spanish average wage (in 2022).

Referring to part-time and full-time staff (i.e. less than 30h/week or more than 37.5h/week), the ratio of permanent full-time staff to the three partners is well above the national average.

The Equal Opportunities/ Discrimination sub-category analyses equal opportunity management practices and discrimination in the opportunities approached within the organisation context. In our cases, the proportion of women varies: 47.37%, 66.67% and 28% respectively (ES: 54.7%). This lower performance - in relation to the national average - might be explained because in this industry the proportion of women staff is typically lower than male staff.

⁷ Últimos datos de siniestralidad

⁸ RD39/1997 - *Reglamento de los Servicios de Prevención*

⁹ <https://ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=36167>

¹⁰ CREM - RELACIONES LABORALES - 2. Convenios colectivos. Evolución de los convenios, trabajadores afectados y variación salarial pactada, según sección de actividad.

¹¹ <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2022/06/seven-experts-explain-how-to-create-fairer-wages/>

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The **Health and Safety Impact** subcategory includes three indicators: 1) Occupational safety measures; 2) Lost time injury frequency rate; and 3) the Presence of sufficient safety measures. The three organizations perform very well in these three indicators. It is especially relevant to notice that none of them have reported injured personnel in work-related incidents in the last year.

Since 1950, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the World Health Organisation (WHO) have shared a common definition of **occupational health**:

“Occupational health should aim at: the promotion and maintenance of the highest degree of physical, mental and social well-being of workers in all occupations; the prevention amongst workers of departures from health caused by their working conditions; the protection of workers in their employment from risks resulting from factors adverse to health; the placing and maintenance of the worker in an occupational environment adapted to his physiological and psychological capabilities; and, to summarize, the adaptation of work to man and of each man to his job” [25].

Besides, within the “social benefits, legal issues” subcategory, we evaluated if the organisations comply with the current regulations in terms of employment, reporting zero reported violations of laws and employment regulations in the ViSS cases. Concerning **Workers’ rights**¹², the VISS SO-LCA measures it by the placement of Collective Bargaining Agreements (CBA); cases 1 and 2 have a signed CBA (at the moment of this evaluation).

Lastly, in our assessment, the aspect **“Sexual harassment”**¹³ was measured with the indicator sexual harassment incidents reported as a means of verification of whether the company registers or not the number of this type of incidents. No sexual harassment incidents were reported.

Table 5 Workers dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
Organisation average wage, per month	4,422.3 €	4
Full-time staff	93%	4
Gender equality	47%	3
Occupational safety measures	1	3
Lost time injury frequency rate	0	3
Presence of sufficient safety measures	1	3
Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	0	3
Collective Bargaining Agreement	67%	3
Sexual harassment incidents reported	0	3

¹² Workers and employers have the right to establish and to join organisations of their choice, without prior authorization, to promote and defend their respective interests, and to negotiate collectively with other parties.

¹³ https://www.ilo.org/sites/default/files/wcmsp5/groups/public/%40dgreports/%40gender/documents/briefingnote/wcms_738115.pdf

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In general, the analysis revealed a greater social performance in the workers dimension, compared to the national reference data. However, gender representation and workers’ rights remain as improvement areas.

5.2.1.2 Stakeholder category: VALUE CHAIN ACTORS

The value chain category was evaluated through a relationship-focused approach by asking about fair competition, social responsibility (SRC) and economic fairness as shown in Table 6. Table 7 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator.

Table 6 Value chain category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Fair competition	NEGATIVE	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	0	0	0	Cases opened by the National Commission for Markets and Competition at the national level		The reference law is 1/2002, of February 21, on antitrust ¹⁴ .
						4(MU); 87 (ES) [37]	2023	
Promoting social responsibility	POSITIVE	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	0	0	1	Companies that plan to implement CSR agreements/ guides in Spain		Existence in the organisation of a CSR agreement.
						41% [38]	2024	
Promoting social responsibility	POSITIVE	Suppliers SCR audit	0	0	0	Percentage of companies with SCR policies and certifications		Recent grey literature was consulted for determining the number of companies formally integrating SCR within their supply processes
						0.01% (n2989/N=3207580 companies ES) [39]; ≈1% [40]; MU: 41 Companies SCR 2024	2024	
Supplier relationships	POSITIVE	Suppliers’ communication relationship	5	5	5	29% (ES); ISO 14001: (ES 2018) >26000 orgs. ; total (ES 2014) 2413 [41] [42] [43]	2019, 2021	Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: coercive communication to 6: very fluent communication)
Wealth distribution	POSITIVE	Fair price definition	0	0	1	No data available		Existence of a policy for deciding a fair price.

Fair competition is key in supporting economic growth and innovation¹⁵. None of the three organizations have reported sanctions for antitrust behaviour, and all cases demonstrated compliance with competition regulations.

¹⁴ Ley 1/2002, de 21 de febrero, de Coordinación de las Competencias del Estado y las Comunidades Autónomas en materia de Defensa de la Competencia.

¹⁵ <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/competitive-and-fair-markets.html>

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The aspect “**Promotion of social responsibility**” assesses whether the value chain organisations promote social responsibility among their suppliers and through their actions. In the VISS framework we use two indicators to assess this: Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility and Suppliers audit. Concerning CSR initiative adoption, the analysis reveals heterogeneous CSR implementation patterns, whilst aligned with the national reference data (i.e., 2693 companies).

To assess the organisations’ **relationship with their suppliers**, ViSS organisations were asked to rate on a scale of 1 (coercive communication) to 6 (very fluent communication) their communication with this group of actors as a proxy for their relationship with their suppliers. Regarding the chain audit mechanism, zero audits across all cases were conducted. The reference data is not considered, regarding the methodological limitation and the comparison between 10-year span data (2014-2024).

Wealth distribution can be explained as how the value is distributed among all the actors of the value chain. An equal distribution is obtained when a fair selling price for a product or service is established. As a proxy of this and to assess this aspect the organisations were asked whether they have defined a specific policy for deciding a fair price. The price fixation mechanism is unevenly distributed, and only one organisation reports to have a specific policy for deciding a fair price for their suppliers.

Table 7 Value chain dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	0	3
Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	33%	2
Suppliers SCR audit	0	0
Suppliers' communication relationship	5	3
Fair price definition	33%	2

The analysis reveals very different performances: competitive compliance and supplier communication overperform, while equal opportunities, supplier audit and fair price definition are areas to be improved. It is relevant to notice a data scarcity for value chain indicators references.

5.2.1.3 Stakeholder category: SOCIETY

The stakeholders’ category Society was analysed by evaluating the sustainability commitment, economic indicators mediated by taxes and R&D investment. Table 8 proposes the scores for each of the three organizations and the reference data, and Table 9 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and an overall score for each Indicator in the Society stakeholder category.

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Table 8 Society category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Public commitment to sustainability issues	POSITIVE	The presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	0	0	0	Percentage of entities that have a sustainability strategy aligned with SDGs	2024	The reference data is set for a sample of 2107 companies.
						29.7% [38]		
Contribution to economic development	POSITIVE	Total taxation per capita	505 449 €/capita (9 603 527 €)	20 000 €/capita (60 000 €)	17 415 €/capita (1 306 101 €)	Tax collection in Spain by budget chapters and taxes (Total chapters I, II, III) per capita	2022	The INE indicates that 159 561.0 million € were collected in 2022 ¹⁶ , considering that there were 20 640 700 ¹⁷ workers the average taxation per capita in Spain was 7 730.04€.
						7,730€ / Total: 159 561 (mill.€) [44]		
Technology development	POSITIVE	Technology transfer	0	0	0	13.5% (Total; 753/5594 companies) [45], [46]	2023	According to the INE data, 753 of 5594 companies transfer results or are beneficiaries of transference
	POSITIVE	Investments in technology development/ transfer	0.00 €	4.425,0 €	4213 812.9 €	% of enterprises, out of total enterprises, with innovation expenditure in 2022, in Spain	2022	INE data (2022) and the demarcation between R&D, technologies and innovation are not well-differentiated
						14.4% [46]		

Our data reveals critical patterns in regard to the sustainability strategy implementation: none of the cases have declared to make available promises or agreements on sustainability issues. It is close to the national average: in 2024, only 2.107 companies out of 3 255 276¹⁸ have declared to have a sustainability strategy aligned with the SDG (0.06%).

In regard to the corporate taxes paid, all cases demonstrate a significantly greater economic contribution and fiscal responsibility. ViSS value chain components have a total taxation per capita higher than the national average, and also a remarkable variation in taxation contributions:

There is not a technology transfer program across the three cases, **whilst they are involved in EC-funded projects**. It is being assumed that the reporting involves some methodological issues, as long as the EC projects necessarily imply some sort of technology transfer or knowledge sharing. However, a limited reference data availability constrains comparative analysis.

¹⁶ RECAUDACIÓN Y ESTADÍSTICAS DEL SISTEMA TRIBUTARIO ESPAÑOL. 2011-2021 (p.73)

¹⁷ Ocupados por sexo y rama de actividad. Valores absolutos y porcentajes respecto del total de cada sexo(65123)

¹⁸ https://ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736160707&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576550

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There is also a significant heterogeneity in technology development expenditure. Although on a different scale, two of the cases have invested in technology development and/or transfer, reporting a better result when compared to the national reference data (14.38%).

Table 9 Society dimension scoring

	Average	Scoring
The presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	0	0
Total taxation per capita	180 954.6 €	4
Technology transfer	0	0
Investments in technology development/ transfer	1 406 079.3 €	3

In sum, complex patterns in organisational sustainability and economic performance emerged: e.g., heterogeneous innovation investment may suggest a different scale of priorities for the involved organisations in regards the technological advancement. A parallel systematic gap in sustainability strategy formalisation seems to prevail. Thus, there is limited shared knowledge and technology transfer within a context of heterogeneous innovation commitment, whilst the economic development support is higher than the national average. In this dimension, those showed insufficiencies and weaknesses due to the lack or scarcity of data, standardisation of the metrics and limitations concerning the availability of the statistical information at regional and national levels.

5.2.1.4 Stakeholder category: LOCAL COMMUNITY

Local Community stakeholder category consists in the assessment of five key aspects that help to understand how the value chain impacts positively the local community: access to material resources, delocalization and migration, safe and healthy living conditions, community engagement, local employment and secure living conditions. Table 10 presents the scores for each of the three organizations and the reference data, and Table 11 presents a synthesis which proposes the average performance for the three organizations and the overall score for each Indicator in the Local Community stakeholder category.

Table 10 Local community category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Aspect	Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
			1	2	3			
Access to material resources	POSITIVE	Environmental management system	0	0	1	Number of organisations with Community Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) in Spain	2024	Data from companies with a formal CSR system (e.g., BCorp &c.) is considered
			≈1% [40]≈1% [40] n=1009 companies					
Delocalization and migration	POSITIVE	Immigrant workforce rate	0	0	25.3%	Employment rate of foreign nationality in Spain	2024 4Q (ES)	INE; percentage of the occupied migrant population (not merely active, which also includes those seeking employment)
			15% (n=3318/21857) [47]					

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	POSITIVE	Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	0	0	0		Companies with CRS procedures: n2989/N=3207580 companies ES
Safe and healthy living conditions	POSITIVE	Promotion of community health	0	1	1	0.01% [39]; ≈1% [40]	
Community engagement	POSITIVE	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	4	4	5		Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: not very diverse to 6: very diverse)
	POSITIVE	Number of meetings with community stakeholders	3	1	1	No data available	Comparable data were not found ¹⁹
Local employment	POSITIVE	Workforce hired locally	2	1	65	83%[50, p. 25]	SEPE data concerning intra-inter regional geographical mobility (2023)
	POSITIVE	Spending on locally based suppliers	0	0	0	CSR Practices with Suppliers: Always try to buy from local suppliers (Murcia region, sample of 128 companies)	The reference data were extracted by a limited local (Murcia) sample. Results might lack transferability and representativeness. Comparable data is not available[51]
						80%[51]	
Secure living conditions	NEGATIVE	Security complaints by the community	0	0	0	No data available	Specific data on this issue was not found, whilst community complaints in the context of the plastics sector typically focus on environmental contamination and false claims [52]

Only one of the three organizations in ViSS value chain has a certified environmental management system. However, the proportion is higher than the national average - only 1,009 companies were EMAS-certified organisations in 2023 (0.03% ES). The data presents significant variations in workforce integration: the proportion of migrant workers in ViSS value chain is lower than the national average. For instance, case 3 reported 25.33% immigrant workforce (ES: 57,40%). Concerning migrant workforce, a notable absence of formal mechanisms for integrating them emerged across all cases, which may indicate a potential systemic gap in workforce integration and/or limited institutional support mechanisms.

¹⁹ BON Europe (Bioplastics Organisations Network Europe) does not provide figures in regards community's stakeholders and meetings, fairs, etc [48], [49] whilst it seems that the cluster and network is quite active.

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Two out of the three organizations in ViSS value chain have declared to have dedicated financial resources to strengthen community health. There are not data available for the reference data. ViSS value chain members estimate that the Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation is medium to high. The three partners have declared to have participated to several meetings with community stakeholders in the last year. The impact in the community engagement might be explained by their involvement in EU funded projects that imply such activities.

Concerning the local employment, the three members of the ViSS value chain indicate that they have hired at least one worker in the last accounting year. However, there is a significant variation in local workforce engagement due to the organisations' size and characteristics. None of the three members of the value chain have reported legal complaints by the local community in the last accounting year received regarding security concerns.

Table 11 Local community scoring

		Average	Scoring
Environmental management system		33%	4
Immigrant workforce rate	■*	8.4%	1
Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	↑*	0 ↑	2
Promotion of community health		66.7%	4
Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation		4.3	3
Number of meetings with community stakeholders		1.7	3
Workforce hired locally		22.7	2
Spending on locally based suppliers		0	0
Security complaints by the community		0	4

*: The organizational procedures for integration are not in place, and at the same time there are not migrants, neither integration policies

Heterogeneous local community engagement and integration practices arose. The stakeholders' practices and procedures in terms of community engagement and environmental management systems appeared as more advanced than the reference data. Nevertheless, the limited migration workforce integration and the absence of suppliers' audit formalised system may lead to further sustainability and organisational issues.

5.2.1.5 Stakeholder category: CONSUMERS

The consumers' assessment examined quality management, transparency and end-of-life systems and responsibilities in the three organizations sampled, as well as the national reference data (Table 12 and Table 13 which presents the average performance of ViSS value chain and the score for each Indicator).

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Table 12 Consumers category: aspects, indicators and reference data

Social influence	Indicators	Organization			Reference	Year	Comments
		1	2	3			
Health and safety	POSITIVE	Labelling	NA	NA	1	Mandatory RD 1055/2022 [53]	Labelling for consumer goods is strictly regulated: it does not apply to cases 1 and 2
	NEGATIVE	Consumer complaints	0	0	0	No data available	Recent data concerning consumers' complaints concerning environmental hazards, packaging defects, public health issues, & applicable to similar organisations/business models is not available.
	POSITIVE	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	1	1	1	Number of ISO 9001 certificates in Spain GFSI : ≈15.7% ES (n=6,067) [54] ISO 9001 : ES n=30 341 [55]	Data from GFSI certifications (including IFS Packaging certification), and ISO 9001 is considered
Transparency	POSITIVE	Organisation communication transparency	6	6	6	% of companies in the region of Murcia that communicate information to their customers with full transparency (sample of 128 companies)	Likert scale: 1 to 6 (1: not very transparent communication to 6: very transparent communication)
						86% ²⁰	
End-of-life responsibility	POSITIVE	Internal management systems	1	1	NA	GFSI : ≈15.7% [54] ISO 9001 : ES n=30 341. Total:3.2mill (≈1%) [55] Management of plastics' end-of-life: mandatory for consumer goods: RD 1468/1988	This is mandatory for food and packaging. However, GFSI certifications for plastics/pack and ISO extend the internal management procedures.

Please, notice that the labelling indicator does not apply to two organisations (ie., they do not sell products to the general public or industry. None of the partners have received consumer complaints in the last year. The three partners declare to follow a quality and/or product safety management system, being above the national reference data. All cases declare to have a very transparent communication towards consumers. In regards the end-of-life responsibility, two partners declare to have internal management systems to ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options (not applicable to one of them).

²⁰

<https://www.um.es/documents/4156512/13232792/Baro%CC%81metro+de+la+RSC+en+Pymes+de+la+Regio%CC%81n+de+Murcia+%28enero+2022%29.pdf/5b1fc119-24eb-6ca3-8d7f-d743c2ce3770?t=1654095930237>

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Table 13 Consumers scoring

	Average	Scoring
Labelling	1*	4
Consumer complaints	0	4
Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	1	4
Organisation communication transparency	6	4
Internal management systems	1	3

5.2.2 SO-LCA: Synthesis and conclusions

Within each analytic category, a summary table comprising the results against the reference data was provided; this section reflects on the first 18 months of the project. For this first report, 3 organizations and 34 indicators were analysed; the major hardship was to find accurate and recent reference data metrics, comparable and updated. The lack of data might undermine the comparison and performance evaluation, as well as the assessment of effects and impacts. But the present exercise has been the opportunity to set the basis for this comparison. Figure 10 recapitulates the areas in which ViSS value chain outperforms or that need improvement in comparison to the reference data.

Figure 10 Overview of improvements areas and strengths observed in the three organisations

The mid-term assessment reveals how certain dimensions demonstrate excellence (quality management, transparency), while others present significant variation (technology investment, workforce integration) and highly differentiated organisational maturity across social performance dimensions. These differences might be explained by the nature of the industry in which these organisations evolved (for instance, the higher wage than the national average might be explained by the characteristics of the sector that tend to employ more specialized personnel but also the low women presence in the organizations' staff).

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Therefore, although preliminary, this first assessment, compiled in Table 14, has been the opportunity to point out at areas where ViSS value chain performs well, but also areas that should be closely monitored for improvement. The colours correspond to the scoring (as mentioned in Figure 2): 0: red, 1: orange, 2: yellow, 3: green, 4: blue.

Table 14 Preliminary SO-LCA Results

CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	Scoring
Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month	Blue
	Working hours	Full-time staff	Blue
	Equal opportunities...	Gender equality	Green
	Health and safety	Occupational safety measures	Green
		Lost time injury frequency rate	Green
	Social benefits...	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	Green
	Workers' rights...	Collective Bargaining Agreement	Green
	Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	Green
Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	Green
	Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	Yellow
		Suppliers audit	Red
	Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship	Green
	Wealth distribution	Fair price definition	Yellow
Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	Red
		Total taxation per capita	Blue
	Technology development	Technology transfer	Red
		Investments in technology development/ transfer	Green
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system	Blue
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate	Yellow
		Organisational procedures to integrate migrant workers	Orange
	Safe and healthy living	Promotion of community health	Blue
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups...	Yellow
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders	Green
	Local employment	Workforce hired locally	Green
		Spending on locally based suppliers	Yellow
Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	Blue	
Consumers	Health and safety	Labelling	Green
		Consumer complaints	Blue
		Quality or Product Safety Management System	Blue
	Transparency	Organisation communication transparency	Blue
	End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems	Green

From a methodological point of view, weaknesses, limitations and challenges appeared. On the one hand, at the present stage the organisations' context is narrow, and its representativeness is limited. In that sense, future assessments (in M33 and M47) will be key as they will help explore the scale-up potential. On the other hand, the SO-LCA is evaluated at organisation-level, excluding the product/s. It may imply that most indicators focus on internal structures – e.g., governance mechanisms and labour policies in place, apart from those mandatory – and the stakeholders' relationship (e.g., suppliers, consumers, society and local community). It may be a hardship if S-LCA proxy data is encountered and used for reference data for the results. Lastly, the limitation in terms of proxy data and availability of corporate and internal organisations' information suppose a

challenge when interpreting the advances towards a safer and more sustainable organisation, products and corporate approach.

Given the scarcity of data, to compile different use cases from the literature, even other EU or Nationally funded project might be required. Indicators seem to be sufficient given the products-organisation dyad and approach, whilst the few cases available complicate the extraction of conclusions.

6 Life Cycle Cost analysis (LCC)

LCC methodology involves a thorough economic assessment of all the costs associated with a product (an asset, product, or service) throughout its entire life cycle and for all the actors of the value chain. This includes the acquisition of raw materials, moving through processing and maintenance, and ending with final disposal or product delivery, all within a defined time frame.

The implementation of the LCC follows a four-step process (Figure 11) that starts with setting the objectives and reach, then assess the estimated costs, aggregate them and, finally, interpret the results. The nature of the SSbD, and within in the LCC, is to assess the design and building processes and modify them if the sustainability score is lower that the aimed objectives. This is why the last stage of the process is the implementation of modifications (if considered necessary); this might imply restarting the LCC process.

Figure 11 LCC four-step process (adapted from Ihobe 2017²¹)

²¹

https://www.steam.euskadi.eus/contenidos/documentacion/guia_lca_lcc/es_def/adjuntos/Guia_%20aplicacion_conjunta_LCC_LCA_cas t.pdf

In LCC methodology, the cost-effectiveness of alternative product or processes, considering all relevant economic factors both in terms of initial costs and future operational costs, are assessed to determine the most efficient. Therefore, LCC methodology is used to identify the impact of products and services to select the best alternatives. The building sector, where high investment is required, has been key in the implementation of LCC [56]. Other guidelines and standards have been developed:

- **Dependability management:** IEC 60300-3-3:2017²² - Part 3-3: Application guide - Life cycle costing
- **Petroleum and natural gas industries:** ISO 15663-2021 [57] – Life cycle costing
- **Standard Practice for Life Cycle Cost:** ASTM F2687-13(2019)²³ - Analysis of Commercial Food Service Equipment.
- **Environmental impacts:** ISO 14008:2019 [58] - Monetary evaluation

There are three types of LCC assessments that range from considering only the internal costs to the costs supported by the social sphere (see Figure 12). The conventional LCC (**cLCC**) includes an assessment of the internal costs of production, the environmental LCC (**eLCC**) includes the costs supported by all the actors of the life cycle of the product and includes the internalization of some external costs assumed by these actors, finally, the societal LCC (**sLCC**) includes the evaluation of other external costs that are supported by society at large (for instance, the costs associated to water contamination).

Figure 12 Alternative types of LCC

ViSS LCC follows the eLCC which relies on the basic life cycle perspective of the LCA and its output. The eLCC includes the monetization of the environmental impacts linked to each life cycle step of the products. For doing so, specific methods are used and internal cost assessed in the cLCC will be included. ViSS LCC will also include the assessment of external costs to meet eLCC requirements. In addition, the possibility of undertaking a sLCC in future assessments will be explored.

²² <https://webstore.iec.ch/en/publication/31206>

²³ <https://www.astm.org/f2687-13r19.html>

6.1 Goal and Scope

The goal of the presented deliverable is to compare the associated economic (cLCC) and environmental costs (eLCC) over the entire life cycle of the **innovative PHBV value chain for food packaging applications**, in comparison with the conventional product already found in the market (Figure 13). ViSS LCC is framed by D6.3 *SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework* which has set the overarching principles, aspects and indicators initially targeted by the assessment. The eLCC considers the conventional costs and the monetization of environmental externalities evaluated in the LCA (Section 3).

Figure 13 ViSS project and conventional solution for comparison

6.1.1 Functional/declared unit and system boundary

The definition of a functional unit is essential in Life Cycle assessment as it works as a common reference unit that allows us to relate and compare the inputs and outputs involved in the solution. The functional unit defined for the LCA is also used for the eLCC and it covers the function, quantity, duration and degree of quality of ViSS solution. The objective being to have a coherent analysis. However, when it is not possible to define precisely a functional unit a declared unit is set. At the present stage of the project in ViSS a functional unit is used, and it will be 1kg of raw PHBV (Table 15).

Table 15 ViSS solution and conventional solution for comparison

ViSS solution	Conventional solution	Functional unit
Innovative PHBV value chain for food packaging	Conventional food packaging	1kg of raw PHBV

ViSS system boundaries (see Section 2) defined for the LCA include the condition of the input for their fermentation to the PHBV drying for later elaboration of the food packaging; therefore, a portion of the final cradle-to-gate approaches. At the present stage of the project, this includes (other stages will be later included):

- Conditioning of sugar rich liquor waste streams
- Hydrolisis of bones and feathers
- Fermentation
- Separation of propionic acid
- Purification
- PHBV production

- Separation of PHBV enriched biomass
- Drying
- Solid-liquid extraction
- PHBV drying

6.2 Inventory & procedure methodology

ViSS eLCC follows the same structure of the LCA with the objective of including the environmental externalities. Considering the present stage of the project, the cost data are not yet known. It will consist in primary data retrieved from the real case studies when this exists and from the literature when this is missing within ViSS value chain (Table 16).

Table 16 Costs considered for ViSS LCC in M18

Raw material cost		Acquisition of waste stream input
Production cost (other inputs and operating costs)	Water	Water consumption cost for the facility and systems
	Energy	Energy consumption cost for the facility and systems (including: electricity, thermal energy and natural gas used in the production process) - <i>not included yet in the LCA</i>
	Carbon dioxide to air	Associated cost to emitted carbon dioxide during the manufacturing process - <i>not included yet in the LCA</i>
	Transport	Cost of freight, cartage, transit insurance and cost of operating fleet and other incidental charges
	Equipment (capital cost)	Purchase cost associated with the equipment necessary to the production
	Installation	Cost of installing the systems and equipment
	Labour cost	Needed man-hours associated with production
	Maintenance	Cost of maintaining the production capacity of the facility and equipment

6.3 Data gathering and data assumptions

The data gathered for ViSS eLCC will be, as mentioned above, primary data collected by the means of questionnaires to the organizations involved in ViSS value chain. The collection of this data will be undertaken by KVC using tables such as presented in Figure 14 and it will consider different assumptions developed below: the Service Life of the product and the period of analysis, the Discount rate and inflation rate and the Environmental externalities.

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Purchase costs of raw materials (inputs) (assumption of purchase cost of raw materials)

Is there a purchase cost of raw materials at this stage? Yes/No

Input	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Observations
TOTAL			0		

Transport costs of materials (inputs - outputs)

Is there an associated transport cost of materials? Yes/No

Transport service - input	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation
Transport (raw material)			
TOTAL	0		

Transport service - output	Service costs (€)	Service cost per ton	Observation
Transport (innovative PHBV)			
TOTAL	0		

Figure 14 Example of data collection questionnaire for ViSS eLCC

ViSS eLCC data will be assessed considering the following assumptions:

Service Life of the product and period of analysis:

The expected life of a product is a key characteristic to analyse as it has a huge impact on the life cycle analysis as all the costs occurring in its lifespan should be taken into account. Therefore, knowing the service life of the product is key in LCC. In the case of ViSS solutions, food packaging, a year is considered to be acceptable. For other sectors, for instance in car industry or the building sector, the considered service life of the asset should be much longer.

The period of analysis refers to the specific analysed time horizon. For some assets, such as in the building sector, it can be lower than the expected service life. Knowing the period of analysis is key in the calculation of the residual value of the product which is the value remaining at the end of the period of analysis. Due to the characteristics of ViSS solutions, which will be a disposable, the period of analysis will be the same as the service life of the product and, therefore, its residual value will be zero.

Discount rate and inflation rate:

The discount rate and the inflation rate are important assumptions to consider in eLCC as they affect the effective cost of investments. But these vary following the nature of the product.

Calculating the discount rate is a way to measure the present value of future investments; this is a way of knowing the rate of return that companies expect on the investment. As the life cycle costs are discounted to their present value, selecting a suitable discount rate for the period of analysis is a crucial decision in an eLCC. In ViSS, the discount rate will not be considered due to the small unitarian value of each individual package and because the lifespan will be a maximum of one year. Knowing the expected inflation rate is important for products that have a long lifespan, in the case of ViSS solution that has a service life of maximum one year the inflation rate will not be considered.

Environmental externalities:

The environmental externalities are a translation in economic terms of the environmental impacts of the product during its lifespan. In ViSS externalities will be calculated using the Environmental Prices method [59]. Environmental Prices method was developed to translate the environmental impacts of a product into monetary terms and a measure to express the amount of environmental impacts of a product based on the cost of preventing that burden. In ViSS the LCA will be used to translate the identified negative externalities of the value chain into monetary terms in Euros.

6.4 LCC implementation (preliminary): Results & conclusions

As presented in Section 5.1, ViSS LCC builds on the LCA (see Section 3) with the objective of assessing the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the input and output included in the LCA model. The general costs considered for assessment in the present LCC are presented in Table 16.

6.4.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

ViSS LCC assesses the same categories as the LCA but focusing on the related costs. The assessed costs are the raw materials used, and the costs related to the materials outputs, the water consumed in the production process, and the carbon dioxide emitted into the air. The physical input and output conventional costs are collected as shown in Table 17.

Table 17 Physical input and output conventional costs

Input	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned chain stage	value	Observations
Water	-	-	1.1692	PHBV production	-	-
Energy	-	-	14.78	PHBV production	-	-
Energy	-	-	3.96	Separation	-	-
Energy	-	-	1.26	Drying	-	-
Energy	-	-	5.6	Solid-liquid extraction	-	-
Output	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned chain stage	value	Observations
Waste produced	-	-	-	-	-	-
...						

6.4.2 Transport costs

The transport costs will also be assessed and collected in a way like Physical input and output conventional costs in Table 18.

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Table 18 Transport costs involved in ViSS value chain

Transport	Amount	Unit	Cost (€)	Concerned value chain stage	Observations
Transport (input)	-	-	60	Conditioning	-
Transport (input)	-	-	60	Hydrolysis	-
...					

6.4.3 Equipment, installation and amortization costs

The equipment costs considered in ViSS LCC include the acquisition of the equipment, the installation costs as well as the amortization cost. The calculation methods will be defined once the equipment is effectively acquired and its use (production / year) and its lifespan are defined (Table 19). We could gather Equipment costs that include the installation costs; however, the amortization costs are not yet included. This will be done in future versions of the LCC.

Table 19 Equipment costs including related installation costs (until M18)

Equipment costs (including installation and amortization costs)	Concerned value chain stage / process	Cost (€) /unit	Cost (€)	Observations
300 L Bioreactor	PHBV production	-	45 761.4	3 units
Tangential filtration	Separation	25 ,760	25 760	1 unit
Evaporator DRY100	Drying	34 500	34 500	1 unit
Soxhlet 2L	Solid-liquid extraction	-	90 764.7	2 units
Evaporator DRY1000	PHBV drying	-	5,000	1 unit
...				

6.4.4 Labour costs

Labour costs will be estimated considering the cost of the work effort in hours needed to produce 1 tonne of material (this will be translated into the labour costs needed to produce 1kg of material).

6.4.5 Maintenance costs

The maintenance costs will be calculated on a yearly basis and will include preventive maintenance activities and reparation costs. These costs will be linked to the equipment involved in ViSS value chain.

Table 20 Maintenance costs included in ViSS eLCC

Maintenance costs	Concerned value chain stage / process	Cost (€)	Observations
Drying equipment	Drying	2,900	-
Extraction equipment	Solid-liquid extraction	3,864.8	-
...			

6.4.6 Plastic chain: total eLCC

This section will compile the costs for producing 1kg of dried biomass enriched with PHBV. These costs will be combined in a table similar to Table 20.

Table 21 Combined table for costs included in ViSS eLCC

eLCC Cost category	Value chain stage										Total
	Conditioning	Hydrolysis	Fermentation	Separation	Purification	PHBV production	Separation	Drying	Solid-liquid extraction	PHBV drying	
Raw material costs	0	0				0	0	0	0	0	0
Water	0	0				1.1692€	0	0	0	0	1.1692€
Energy - <i>not included yet in the LCA</i>	TBD	TBD				14.78€	3.96	1.26	5.6	TBD	25 604€
Carbon dioxide into the air - <i>Not included in the LCA</i>	TBD	TBD				TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Transport related costs	60	60				0	0	0	0	0	120€
Equipment, installation and amortization costs	0	TBD				45.761.4€	25 760€	34 500€	90.764.7€	5.000€	298 150.9€
Maintenance costs	0	TBD				0	0	2 900	3 864.8	0	6.764.8€
Labour costs	TBD	TBD				TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Total conventional costs
Environmental costs
Total eLCC	304 915.7€

6.4.7 Comparison with conventional products

A comparison, if possible, will be done of the comparison of total eLCC assessed of dried biomass enriched with PHBV against the conventional product that can be found in the market (Table 22).

Table 22 ViSS solution compared to market conventional product

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
ViSS solution	Dried biomass enriched with PHBV
Conventional product

6.4.8 Limitations to consider for future assessments

At this stage of the project, it is important to acknowledge some limitations that will be addressed in future assessments. ViSS LCC will help build a standardized approach for eLCC which is missing,

especially in food packaging sector. It is too soon to compare the costs of ViSS solution with the existing conventional product, this is why the present deliverable cannot present conclusions on the efficiency of ViSS solution. Associated to that is the existence of relevant uncertainties that should be taken into consideration in future assessments.

This approach will, however, be replicable for other food packaging solutions or other initiatives.

7 Conclusions

The present preliminary sustainability assessment has been undertaken on the basis of the SSbD and Social Readiness evaluation framework (D6.3). This framework has proved to be adapted for the objectives of ViSS project and, although with the pertinent adaptations, will continue to be used during the project's lifespan.

The sustainability assessment undertaken for ViSS SSbD has been conditioned by the scarcity of available data. Therefore, this deliverable should be considered as a first approach to future assessments where the TRL will be higher and where ViSS consortium will have more and better data on ViSS value chain. ViSS value chain actors will also be enlarged to include more data in the analysis, see Annex 5. However, the present exercise has already been an opportunity to identify characteristics of ViSS solution to improve to have a performing final ViSS product.

In the **environmental dimension**, this first iteration of LCA is performed to get an overview of the environmental impacts of the process design. In the consecutive iterations, both the LCA will be more in depth as well as the process development more matured. As a main conclusion of the first iteration, the current ViSS PHBV production value chain does not achieve any impact reductions compared to fossil benchmark. Moreover, the impacts of ViSS PHBV are drastically greater than the benchmark even when this first iteration of LCA considered only mass balances of limited parts of the process and therefore lacks the impacts arising from energy consumption and from the rests of the production processes. Therefore, across the ViSS process chain redesign is needed. To reduce the total quantity of chemicals used, it is recommended to improve fermentation yields, reduce the amounts of solvents used and utilize regeneration, circulation and re-usage of chemicals. Reductions on chemicals used will simultaneously lower the production costs. Energy efficiency of equipment and production methods should be considered when upscaling the ViSS production from pilot to demo scale.

In the consecutive LCA and eSbD iterations, it is wise to consider other benchmarks alongside the fossil polymer. Not just the type of polymer, but the quality and technical/mechanical properties should be considered, when addressing the benchmark. Thus, the functional unit may have to consider e.g. the density or thickness of the materials in packaging applications instead of the mass used in this phase of the study. To unify the system boundaries of LCA on both the ViSS PHBV and benchmark polymer, the LCA of benchmark might require separate modelling by VTT. Also, in the

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consecutive LCA iterations, the use-stage and end-of-life stage of polymers should be included to the system boundary in order to study the effect of VISS PHBV biodegradation.

Although this first **social dimension** assessment is fragmentary, the available retrieved data are encouraging and it was the opportunity to rehearse the ViSS scoring system (scores, and related code colour, given to each indicator from 0 to 4 following their social performance against comparative context data). The assessment of ViSS value chain highlights key areas for improvement, including migrant workforce integration, supplier audits, CSR policies, governance structures, knowledge transfer, societal awareness, and collaborative research. In addition, the SO-LCA evaluation reveals challenges, such as a narrow organizational context and limited representativeness, making it difficult to scale results until ViSS solutions does not reach a higher TRL. Proxy data usage for comparative analysis poses further difficulties. Limited data availability complicates interpretation of progress towards a more sustainable organization and product approach. Finally, the focus on organizational-level evaluation, excluding products, restricts the scope of indicators, especially concerning internal structures and stakeholder relationships. To address these issues, additional use cases from literature and EU or nationally funded projects may be needed, as the available cases make it difficult to draw clear conclusions.

For the **economic dimension**, the basis for the LCC is set and in the next related deliverable in M33 (D6.10 Interim sustainable by design assessment), when the TRL will be higher and more information will be made available, it will be possible to undertake the economic assessment of ViSS solution. As mentioned above it will be closely related to the LCA. So far only a part of the future costs has been reported as the available information on costs is limited at this TRL.

Although ViSS sustainability assessment is so far only preliminary and the scoring system is still underdeveloped and not systematized for all dimensions, these results set the conditions to start feeding ViSS ICT Tool (D6.4 and D6.5) that will present the score for individual Indicators or Aspects (see Table 22) or by Category (see Figure 15).

Table 23 Evaluation of Environmental and Social Aspects and Indicators

DIMENSION	CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	Sc.
ENVIRONMENTAL	Toxicity	Ecotoxicity: freshwater		
		Ecotoxicity: freshwater, inorganics		
		Ecotoxicity: freshwater, organics		
		Human toxicity: carcinogenic		
		Human toxicity: carcinogenic, inorganics		
		Human toxicity: carcinogenic, organics		
		Human toxicity: non-carcinogenic		
		Human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, inorganics		
		Human toxicity: non-carcinogenic, organics		
	Climate change	Climate change		
		Climate change: biogenic		
		Climate change: fossil		
		Climate change: land use and land use change		
	Pollution	Acidification		
		Eutrophication: freshwater		
Eutrophication: marine				

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		Eutrophication: terrestrial			
		Ionising radiation: human health			
		Ozone depletion			
		Particulate matter formation			
		Photochemical oxidant formation: human health			
		Energy resources: non-renewable			
		Resource use	Land use		
			Material resources: metals/minerals		
			Water use		
SOCIAL	Workers	Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month		
		Working hours	Full-time staff		
		Equal opportunities...	Gender equality		
		Health and safety	Occupational safety measures		
			Lost time injury frequency rate		
		Social benefits...	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations		
		Workers' rights...	Collective Bargaining Agreement		
		Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported		
	Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour		
		Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility		
Suppliers audit					
Supplier relationships		Suppliers' communication relationship			
Wealth distribution	Fair price definition				
Society	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues			
	Contributions to eco. dev.	Total taxation per capita			
	Technology development	Technology transfer			
		Investments in technology development/ transfer			
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system			
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate			
		Organisational procedures to integrate migrant workers			
	Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health			
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups...			
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders			
	Local employment	Workforce hired locally			
	Secure living conditions	Spending on locally based suppliers			
Consumers	Health and safety	Security complaints by the community			
	Health and safety	Labelling			
		Consumer complaints			
		Quality or Product Safety Management System			
	Transparency	Organisation communication transparency			
End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems				

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Figure 15 Combined evaluation for LCA and SO-LCA Categories

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Annexes:

Annex 1 The processes used in the LCA model

The ecoinvent 3.10 process used in the LCA Sulca 5.3 model (summary table):

Material	ecoinvent 3.10 process
Sugar rich liquor waste	-
Bones and feathers	-
Sodium hydroxide	market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state, RER
Distilled water	market for tap water, Europe without Switzerland
IRIS culture media ingredient 1	market for glucose, GLO
IRIS culture media ingredient 2	market for fodder yeast, GLO
IRIS culture media ingredient 3	market for fodder yeast, GLO
Distilled water	market for water, decarbonised, ES
IRIS solvent 1	market for fatty acid, GLO
IRIS solvent 2	market for chemical, organic, GLO
Sodium chloride	market for sodium chloride, powder, GLO
Magnesium dichloride hexahydrate	market for magnesium chloride, from titanium sponge production, GLO
Magnesium sulfate	market for magnesium sulfate, GLO
Calcium chloride dihydrate	market for calcium chloride, RER
Potassium chloride	market for potassium chloride, RER
Sodium bicarbonate	market for sodium bicarbonate, RER
Sodium bromide	-
Iron(III) chloride	market for iron(III) chloride, without water, in 40% solution state, GLO
Potassium hydroxide	market for potassium hydroxide, GLO
Hydrochloric acid	market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state, RER
Polypropylene (benchmark)	market for polypropylene, granulate, GLO

Annex 2: Questionnaires to organizations in ViSS value chain for the So-LCA

Purpose & Confidentiality disclosures

This questionnaire is intended to gather the required information to perform the Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment entitled in the ViSS project under the Task 6.4.

The data you provide through this questionnaire will only be used for the ViSS project purposes, under no circumstances will be passed on to third parties. This data will be managed by José Benedicto Royuela & the staff of SENIOR EUROPA S.L. (with commercial brand Kveloce). You can exercise your rights of access, modification or deletion of data by sending an email to jbenedicto@kveloce.com

Please include your name and surname: _____

Position in the organization: _____

General company information²⁴ Please complete the following gaps with the organization information:

Last accounting year	
Total company workforce in the last accounting year	
Nº of injuries in the last accounting year	
Total number of hours worked by employees in the last accounting year	

Human Resources Department

I2-W2 Indicate the living wage in euros per month (i.e., the monthly wage needed to cover the necessary living costs of an individual or family, for example the minimum living income) of the region/ nation

I2-W3 Indicate the minimum wage (i.e., the lowest gross wage a full-time worker can be remunerated in a specific country, defined by national law and legally binding) in the region in euros

I2-W4 Please indicate in euros the organisation average wage in nominal terms, per month in the last accounting year

I3-W5 Please indicate the number of full-time permanent staff in the organisation in the last accounting year

I4-W6 Please indicate the total number of women working in the workforce of the organisation in the last accounting year

²⁴ Please keep in mind when completing the questionnaire that all the information is referred to the last accounting year

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I5-W8 Include the number of injured persons (work-related incident) in the last accounting year in your company

I5-W9 Does your company comply with the safety measures obligations required according to your applicable law?

Elija un elemento.

I6-W10.1 Has your organisation been sanctioned in the last accounting year for non-compliance with current legislation or labour regulations?

Elija un elemento.

I6-W10.2 If yes, how many? Please indicate the number of sanctions in the last accounting year:

I7-W11.1.1 Does your organisation has collective bargaining agreements signed at the moment?

Elija un elemento.

I.7-W11.1.2 If yes, are the collective bargaining agreement and meeting minutes available for workers (i.e., copies of collective bargaining negotiations and agreements are kept on file)?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.2.1 Are there labour organizations(trade union delegates) in the company?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.2.2 If yes, is their presence adequately supported? (i.e., availability of facilities to union, posting of union notices, time to exercise the representation functions on paid work hours)

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.3 Are the employee/union representatives invited to contribute to planning of large changes in the company (such as launching a new department for example), which affect the working conditions?

Elija un elemento.

I7-W11.4 Do workers have access to a neutral, binding, and independent dispute resolution procedure?

Elija un elemento.

I1-W1 How many persons work, or provide services in your company under the menace of any penalty and from which the said person has not offered himself or herself voluntarily? Please indicate the number:

I8-W12. Indicate the number of sexual harassment incidents reported within the organization in the last accounting year

I3-LC3 Please complete the following gap with the required information

Number of immigrants in the organization workforce in the last accounting year	
--	--

I7-LC10 Please indicate the total number of locally hired workers in the last accounting year (the local labour market has the characteristic of containing within its borders most of the residence-labour flows of its population.):

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Finance and Administration Department

I1-VC1.1 Has your institution been sanctioned for unfair competition (anti-competitive behaviour)?

Elija un elemento.

I1-VC1.2 If yes, please indicate the number of sanctions in the last accounting year:

I2-VC3 Please indicate the following

{VC3.1} Number of hired suppliers audited with regard to social responsibility in the last year accounting year	_____
{VC3.2} Number of hired suppliers in the last accounting year	_____

I3-VC4 Please, indicate how would you rate the relationship with the organization suppliers:

1 Coercive communication	2	3	4	5	6 Very fluent communication

I4-VC5 Please indicate the number of conflicts that arose due to the use of local intellectual property:

I2-S2 Indicate in euros the total amount of taxes (all the paid taxes including VAT, social security contributions, Tax on Economic Activities, Corporate income tax, IRPF) paid in the last accounting year

I3-S4 Please complete the following gaps with the required information:

{ I3-S4.1} Last accounting year investment in euros in technology development and/or transfer	_____
{ I3-S4.2} Last accounting year total organisation investment in euros	_____

I5-LC6 Has your organization dedicated financial resources (in €) to strengthen community health (i.e., through shared community access to organization health resources)?

NO

I6-LC7 How diverse are the stakeholder engaged with the organization?

1 Not very diverse	2	3	4	5	6 Very diverse

I6-LC8 How many meetings have been done in the last accounting year with community stakeholders?

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I6-LC9.1 How many volunteer-hours of organizational support have been provided for community initiatives?

I6-LC9.2 How many financial resources (in €) have been provided for community initiatives?

I7-LC11 Please complete the following gap with the required information:

{I7-LC11.1} Spendings without taxes of the last accounting year in euros on locally based suppliers	_____
{I7-LC11.2} Total amount of spending without taxes on suppliers (in euros)	_____

AGREEMENTS & SPECIFIC PROGRAMMS

I2-VC2 Does your intuition has a Corporate Social Responsibility agreement?

Elija un elemento.

I4-W7 Do formal policies on equal opportunities exist in the organisation, such as Gender Equality Plan?

Elija un elemento.

I5-VC6 Does the organisation have a specific policy for deciding a fair price (i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin)?

Elija un elemento.

I1-S1 DoNOes the organization has any public available document as promises or agreements on sustainability issues?

Elija un elemento.

I3-S3 Does you organisation has a technology transfer program, or any project related with results transfer?

Elija un elemento.

I1-LC1 Does your organization have a certified environmental management system?

Elija un elemento.

I3-LC4 Does the organization has any internal procedures to integrate migrant workers into the community?

Elija un elemento.

I1-C3 Does your organization have a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.?

Elija un elemento.

I5-C7 Do you have internal management systems to ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of life options (if applicable)?

Elija un elemento.

CONSUMERS

I8-LC12 Please indicate the number of legal complaints by the local community in the last accounting year received with regard to security concerns

I1-C1 Does your products have informative labels?

Elija un elemento.

I1-C2 How many consumer complaints have your organization received in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organization?

I3-C5 Please indicate the number of consumer complaints related to breach of privacy or loss of data within the last accounting year

I4-C6 Rate the effort of the organization on communicating all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way towards consumers

1 Not very transparent communication	2	3	4	5	6 Very transparent communication

Annex 3: ViSS aspects used in Social Dimension assessment

In **green** preferred options (in **bold green** letters those that have had a score higher than 4,5 in WP6 GA workshop), in **red** less valued options and indicators that are not covered by the project manager questionnaire in M18.

CATEGORY	ASPECT	INDICATOR	VISS GA workshop score	Included in survey to organizations	Used in M18 assessment
Workers	Forced labour	Employment terms	3.32	No	No
		Forced Labour		No	No
	Fair salary	Living wage per month	4.23	Yes	No
		Minimum wage, per month		Yes	No
		Organisation average wage, per month		Yes	Yes
	Working hours	Flexibility	3.73	No	No
		Full-time staff		Yes	Yes
	Equal opportunities/ Discrimination	Gender equality	4.12	Yes	Yes
		Equal opportunities policies		No	No
	Health and safety	Occupational safety measures	4.62	Yes	Yes
		Lost time injury frequency rate		Yes	Yes
	Social benefits, legal issues, social security	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	3.77	Yes	Yes
Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	Trade unions density	4.23	No	No	
	Collective Bargaining Agreement		Yes	Yes	
Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported	3.56	Yes	Yes	
Value chain actors	Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	3.82	Yes	Yes
	Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	3.91	Yes	Yes
		Suppliers audit		Yes	Yes
	Supplier relationships	Suppliers' communication relationship	3.68	Yes	Yes
Wealth distribution	Fair price definition	4.05	Yes	Yes	
Society	Respect intellectual property rights	Number of property rights infringements	-	Yes	No
	Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	4.22	Yes	Yes

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	Contributions to economic development	Total taxation per capita	4.04	Yes	Yes
	Technology development	Technology transfer	4.48	Yes	Yes
		Investments in technology development/ transfer		Yes	Yes
	Corruption (value chain actors)	Corruption	3.39	No	No
	Poverty alleviation	Poverty alleviation programme	3.48	No	No
Local community	Access to material resources	Environmental management system	3.70	Yes	Yes
	Access to immaterial resources	Community education initiatives	3.22	No	No
	Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate	3.61	Yes	Yes
		Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community		Yes	Yes
	Cultural heritage	Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage	3.13	No	No
	Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health	4.74	Yes	Yes
	Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	3.68	Yes	Yes
		Number of meetings with community stakeholders		Yes	Yes
	Local employment	Workforce hired locally	4.39	Yes	Yes
Spending on locally based suppliers		Yes		Yes	
Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community	3.96	Yes	Yes	
Consumers	Health and safety	Labelling	4.68	Yes	Yes
		Consumer complaints		Yes	Yes
		Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System		Yes	Yes
	Feedback mechanism	Presence of consumers feedback mechanism	3.27	Yes	No
	Transparency	Organisation communication transparency	3.73	Yes	Yes
	End-of-life responsibility	Internal management systems	4.50	Yes	Yes
	Affordability	Potential price in comparison to market equivalent	4.24	No	No

Annex 4: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment

Value chain: food packaging industry (mesh bags, trays and bags and envelops)

WORKERS:

Fair salary	
- Organisation average wage	
Definition	Organisation average wage provides information about the mean monthly salaries to assess if the salary is enough to afford a decent standard of living. The indicator is given as the mean of monthly earnings of all employees in the organisation in nominal terms.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	€
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified (A2C D.7.5)</i>

Working hours	
- Flexibility	
Definition	Employee's self-perceived quantification of the extent to which the company provides adequate flexibility for work-life balance, rest and overtime. The indicator provides a synthetic, albeit mainly subjective, measure of different dimensions involved in work-life balance
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale (1 to 6)
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation
Source	D.7.5
- Full-time staff	
Definition	Indicator to see the ratio of full-time permanent staff
Calculation formula	Full-time permanent staff / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Equal opportunities/Discrimination	
- Gender equality	

D6.7 First sustainable by design assessment.v2.0.

Definition	This indicator is intended to measure the percentage of women in the total workforce
Calculation formula	Nº of women / total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method
- Equal opportunities policies	
Definition	This indicator is intended to note the presence of policies aimed at promoting equal opportunities between men and women, such as for example a Gender Equality Plan
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP

Health and safety	
- Occupational safety measures	
Definition	Indicator to assess whether the worker perceives occupational health measures as adequate.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Questionnaire
Level	Organisation - worker
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP
- Lost time injury frequency rate	
Definition	Lost time injury frequency rate, the number of lost time injuries occurring in a workplace per 1 million hours worked.
Calculation formula	Nº of injuries x10 ⁶ / hours worked
Unit	[0, +∞]
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method

Social benefits, legal issues, social security	
- Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations	
Definition	Number of sanctions imposed for non-compliance with current regulations
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}

D6.7 First sustainable by design assessment.v2.0.

	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 <i>Modified</i>

Workers' rights / Freedom of association and collective bargaining	
- Collective Bargaining Agreement	
Definition	All workers and employers have the right to establish and to join organisations of their choice, without prior authorization, to promote and defend their respective interests, and to negotiate collectively with other parties. They should be able to do this freely, without interference by other parties or the state, and should not be discriminated against because of union membership.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Article: Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA) and Organisation 4.0: An easy-to-implement method Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

Sexual harassment	
- Sexual harassment incidents reported	
Definition	This indicator verifies whether the company register the number of sexual harassments incidents.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{1,2} {0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets 2021 (UNEP)

VALUE CHAIN ACTORS:

Fair competition	
- Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour	
Definition	Presence of documented statement or procedures to prevent engaging in or being complicit in anti-competitive behaviour à not applicable à number of sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Promoting social responsibility
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D6.7 First sustainable by design assessment.v2.0.

- Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility	
Definition	Accreditation of Corporate social responsibility compliance
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>
- Suppliers audit	
Definition	Percentage of suppliers the enterprise has audited with regard to social responsibility in the last year
Calculation formula	Number of hired suppliers audited/ number of suppliers hired
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Supplier relationships	
- Suppliers' communication relationship	
Definition	Existence of direct and satisfying relationship with suppliers.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert 0-5
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	A2C

Wealth distribution	
- Fair price definition	
Definition	Indicator to assess whether the price has been defined fairly: Definition of a fair price, i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin; this indicator can be either qualitative and quantitative, the latter calculated through a detailed cost assessment
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, 1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Respect intellectual property rights	
- Number of property rights infringements	
Definition	This indicator is aimed to know if the company have had any type of conflict related with the use of intellectual property at local level
Calculation formula	NA

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Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

SOCIETY:

Public commitment to sustainability issues	
- Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has a public document as promise or agreement on sustainability issues. This information might be complemented with an interview
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, 1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Contributions to economic development	
- Total taxation per capita	
Definition	Total taxes paid in the last year, by all typologies, per capita (organisation). Taxes paid represent a proxy for the social contribution of each company
Calculation formula	Taxation per capita= total taxes paid / total workforce
Unit	€
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Technology development	
- Technology transfer	
Definition	Involvement in technology transfer program or projects. The indicator verifies whether the company is actively involved in technology transfer programs or projects
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>
- Investments in technology development/ transfer	
Definition	Share of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment. This indicator is a proxy for the effort made by the organisation in development and/or technology transfer, as well as the degree of technological innovation that a product incorporates

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Calculation formula	$pi=ni/Ni$ pi : proportion of investment in technology development and/or transfer over total investment items ni : represents the investment in technology development and/or transfer (in euros) of the company Ni : represents the total investment, all items (in euros)
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

LOCAL COMMUNITY:

Access to material resources	
- Environmental management system	
Definition	Presence of a certified environmental management system. The indicator verifies whether the company has a certified environmental management system.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Delocalization and migration	
- Immigrant workforce rate	
Definition	The immigration rate indicates social risks linked with a migrant inflow. The more migrants are in a certain region the more they influence the job market. Therefore, this indicator is intended to calculate the percentage of immigrants in the organisation workflow to be compared at regional level.
Calculation formula	Number of immigrants in the workforce/ total workforce
Unit	%
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	PSILCA V3 Modified
- Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has any internal procedure for integrating migrant workers into the community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Safe and healthy living conditions

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- Promotion of community health	
Definition	Indicator to assess if the company has dedicated resources to promoting community health
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets (UNEP)

Community engagement	
- Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation	
Definition	To which extent the organisation has a diverse stakeholder's community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale 1-6
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP
- Number of meetings with community stakeholders	
Definition	This indicator is intended to know whether the relationship of the organisation with its community stakeholders is recurrent
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological sheets UNEP (<i>modified</i>)

Local employment	
- Workforce hired locally	
Definition	Proportion of locally hired workers over total new hires. The indicator is a proxy of the organisations' involvement with the local workforce
Calculation formula	$pi=ni/Ni$ pi : proportion of locally hired workers ni : number of locally hired workers Ni : total workforce
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>
- Spending on locally based suppliers	
Definition	Proportion of spending on locally based suppliers over total expenditure on materials, equipment and services. The indicator is a proxy for the organisation's involvement with the local supply of goods & services, as well as for the weight of local suppliers in the manufacture of a product

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Calculation formula	$pi=ni/Ni$ pi : proportion of spending on locally-based suppliers of the company ni : spending on locally-based suppliers (in euros) of the company Ni : total amount of spending on suppliers (in euros) of the company
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

Secure living conditions	
- Security complaints by the community	
Definition	Number of legal complaints against the organisation with regard to security concerns by the local community
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,+∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>

CONSUMERS:

Health and safety	
- Labelling	
Definition	Information available regarding features. The existence of labels in the product about its characteristics provides useful information to the consumer
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	A2C D.7.5 <i>modified</i>
- Consumer complaints	
Definition	Number of consumer complaints in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organisation
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0, +∞}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP
- Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System	
Definition	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}

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Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Transparency	
- Organisation communication transparency	
Definition	Organisation effort on communication all issues regarding its products and social responsibility in a transparent way
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	Likert scale 0-6
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

End-of-life responsibility	
- Internal management systems	
Definition	This indicator is intended to know if the company has internal management systems that ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options for products. <i>In a product life cycle, end-of-life refers to product disposal, reuse, or recycling. In an environmental context, this concept is commonly referred to as extended producer responsibility. Product disposal can lead to significant environmental and social concerns.</i>
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1,2}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organisation
Source	Methodological Sheets UNEP

Affordability	
- Potential price in comparison to market equivalent	
Definition	Price proposed comparable to conventional products in the market.
Calculation formula	NA
Unit	{0,1}
Data source	Consultation with industrial partners
Level	Organization
Source	

Annex 5: Enlarged value chain

- **Value chains selection: rationale (retrieved from D7.2 Public engagement strategy)**
 - **Agrifood value chain**

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Food/confectionary producers	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vidal golosinas • Fini golosinas • Caramelos Celdrán • Zukan • Jake 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdulces
Agrifood Clusters and Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agritech Murcia • Fundación Cluster Agroalimentario de la Región de Murcia • Proexport- Asociación de Productores-Exportadores de Frutas y Hortalizas de la Región de Murcia • Fecoam-Federación de Cooperativas Agrarias de Murcia (FECOAM) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FEDACOVA (Federación Empresarial de Agroalimentación de la Comunidad Valenciana)

- **Plastic**

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Private Organisations and Industry	
Plastic converters and recyclers	Plastic converters and recyclers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eversia • Palec Ecológico • Galian Plasticos • Onlyplast Spain • Walki Plasbel • Reciclajes Plásticos • Plastirama • Plasticos Ros Marin • Green World Compounding • Industrias Anfra • Solplast • Puromaster • Servicios Plásticos • Polimur • Cristobal Meseguer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indesla Packaging • Viduca • Termoformados Banyeres • ITC Packaging • Termoformas • Totemplast • GreatPlastic • Juypal Hogar • Plasticol • Sarabia Pack • Plásticos Jijona • Plasticos Francés • <u>Vicedo</u> Martí • Acteco • BSDI

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturas Adelplast • Jokey Ibérica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suinso • Telas minido • Pérez Linares Plastic Solutions • Plásticos Inden • Prepi • Plásticos Acrílicos Alicante
Industrial and Business Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asemuplast (Region of Murcia) • AMIQ (Association of Chemical Industries in the Region of Murcia) • AEMA RM (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVEP (Valencian Association of Plastic Entrepreneurs) • APPA (Association of Plastics in Alicante) • Quimacova (Chemical and Environmental Association of the Chemical sector in Valencian Community) • ANEPMA (Association of Public enterprises in Alicante for environmental management) • CE/R+S- Club of Responsible and Sustainable Enterprises of the Valencian Community

Additional/transversal stakeholders:

MURCIA	ALICANTE
Retailers, Supermarkets, Services	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food chains (Aldi, Mercadona, Lidl, Spar, Superdumbo, Vidal, Más y Más) • SMEs, entrepreneurs (small supermarkets, market vendors, local shops) 	
Industrial and Business Associations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asemuplast (Region of Murcia) • AMIQ (Association of Chemical Industries in the Region of Murcia) • AEMA RM (Environmental Businesses Association-Region of Murcia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVEP (Valencian Association of Plastic Entrepreneurs) • APPA (Association of Plastics in Alicante) • Quimacova (Chemical and Environmental Association of the Chemical sector in Valencian Community) • ANEPMA (Association of Public enterprises in Alicante for environmental management) • CE/R+S- Club of Responsible and Sustainable Enterprises of the Valencian Community
Financing Intermediaries	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caja Rural Central • Caja Rural Regional 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banco Sabadell • La Caixa • Caixa Ontinyent

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Private Non-Profit Organisations

- | | |
|---|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• CETENMA- Technological Centre for Energy and Environment• CEEIM- Business and Technological Centre in Murcia• CEEIC- Business and Technological Centre in Cartagena | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Textile Industry Research Association – AITEX• European Centre of Business and Innovation-Elche• European Centre of Business and Innovation-Alcoy |
|---|---|